

Quality Criteria for Citizen Science Projects on *Österreich forscht*

Version 1.2

Developed by the Quality Criteria Working Group of the Citizen Science Network Austria.

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Preamble

The *Österreich forscht* platform (www.citizen-science.at) was founded in 2014 with the aim of (1) networking citizen science stakeholders in Austria, (2) providing as comprehensive an overview as possible of citizen science projects in Austria, and (3) generally developing the citizen science methodology.

In 2017, on the initiative of the *Österreich forscht* platform, many institutions active in citizen science joined forces in the Citizen Science Network Austria and committed themselves to promoting the quality of citizen science in Austria (<https://www.citizen-science.at/netzwerk>). An important step in promoting quality was the establishment of transparent criteria that projects wishing to be listed on the *Österreich forscht* platform must fulfil. The aim of these criteria is to guarantee and further improve the quality of the projects presented on the platform. This catalogue is the third version (1.2) of the criteria; the previous versions are linked at the end of the preamble.

From March 2017 to February 2018, a working group of the *Österreich forscht* platform, consisting of representatives from 17 institutions, developed version 1.0 of the criteria, which enable a transparent evaluation of projects that want to be listed on *Österreich forscht*. In addition, the criteria should enable citizen scientists to make an informed decision about whether they want to participate in the project. Version 1.0 of the Quality Criteria was presented to the public at the 4th Austrian Citizen Science Conference (ÖCSK) from 1-3 February 2018. The Quality Criteria became valid on this date. Suggestions for changes to the criteria were already made by participants at the 2018 ÖCSK, and were incorporated into version 1.1 by the working group immediately afterwards. Therefore, as of 13 October 2023, all projects on *Österreich forscht* comply with the quality criteria of version 1.1.

During the development of the quality criteria, it was decided that they would continue to be adapted as necessary to meet new challenges and developments. The version number of the criteria to which a project conforms can be found on the project page.

In version 1.2, in particular, the criteria for ethical aspects in citizen science projects have been adapted to current developments in 2024. Regarding the ethical principles that we consider essential for citizen science, we are committed to implementing the [United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights](#), the [World Medical Association \(WMA\) Declaration of Helsinki - Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects](#), and the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) in all its values and principles in our daily work in citizen science.

This includes taking responsibility as an individual. In this context, responsibility as a project leader means respecting and protecting the welfare of people and the living and non-living environment in research. Respectful treatment of all people involved in the citizen science project is a matter of course for us.

In citizen science projects, the aim is to share responsibility fairly among all participants. If there is an unequal distribution of power in a project, for example due to hierarchical structures, unequal distribution of relevant knowledge or other inequalities, it is necessary for the group with more power (usually the project management) to take responsibility for the disadvantaged groups, e.g. to ensure social justice or gender equality.

All of the above will be implemented not only in direct interactions, but also in the digital space. Therefore, all projects are committed to ensuring that they develop or use technologies in the digital space that are consistent with the basic ethical principles mentioned above and the criteria listed below. In addition, all projects will pay attention to data protection, privacy, cybersecurity, freedom of expression and the reduction of digital inequality.

We also encourage the use of open source technologies (<https://opensource.org/osd>) wherever appropriate and possible.

The first part of the criteria is mainly about what constitutes a citizen science project. We have chosen a negative list (i.e. we define everything that is NOT citizen science) in order to keep *Österreich forscht* as open as possible to different concepts, approaches and disciplines. This means that we consider all projects that are not excluded by these criteria to be citizen science projects. The professional background of the person leading the project is not decisive, as long as the project itself meets the criteria. The criteria in the second part should be understood as minimum standards that all projects on *Österreich forscht* must meet.

The evaluation will be carried out by the coordinators of the *Österreich forscht* platform. They will be advised by the members of the working group.

Version 1.0 of the quality criteria: <https://zenodo.org/records/1161953>

Version 1.1 of the quality criteria: <https://zenodo.org/records/3648636>

For the Quality Criteria Working Group, the chairs

Dr. Florian Heigl and Dr. Daniel Dörler

Criteria catalogue

Österreich forscht welcomes all projects, but excludes projects:

- ... with the exclusive participation of persons with a professional-scientific background appropriate to the project.
- ... by professional scientists or scientific institutions in which exclusively people are asked about their opinions, attitudes, lifestyles, etc. are excluded.
- ... by professional scientists or scientific institutions in which exclusively data about the participants are collected.
- ... by professional scientists or scientific institutions, in which the participants are exclusively passive providers of resources.

Citizen science projects on the *Österreich forscht* platform meet the following criteria.

1. A scientific question, or a hypothesis, or an objective must be formulated that can be answered, verified or achieved with the project.
2. The methods must be presented in a subject-specific, appropriate and comprehensible manner.
3. New knowledge must be generated, e.g. an improved explanation of certain relationships must be created, or new methods must be developed.
4. Added value must be generated for all participants (citizen scientists as well as scientists).
5. Achieving the project's aims is impossible without citizen scientists getting involved.
6. Citizen scientists must be involved in at least one project element. Typically, a research project has the following elements
 - Identifying the topic and formulating the research question
 - Method design
 - Data collection
 - Data analysis and interpretation
 - Publication of the results
 - Project governance (control, management and monitoring)
7. The tasks and objectives of the project must be communicated in an open, easy-to-find and generally understandable way.
8. The distribution of roles in the project must be clear and transparent.
9. All data and metadata must be made available to the public, provided there are no legal or research ethics arguments against doing so.
10. The results must be published in an open-access format, provided there are no legal or research ethics arguments against doing so.
11. The results must be findable, reusable, comprehensible and transparent.
12. Different interest groups must be addressed accordingly.
13. Contact details (e.g. email address, phone number or contact form on the home page) for questions or feedback must be easy to find. The possibility of interaction between project management and citizen scientists must be available at all times.
14. The participating citizen scientists must receive feedback on the results and progress of the project.
15. The results must be published in a generally understandable way.
16. Potential conflicts of interest related to the research objectives must be disclosed.
Additional explanation: A conflict of interest exists when the objective research in the citizen science project is influenced by other interests (company goals, association goals, personal interests, etc.).

17. The central method of the project must be reflected upon from an ethical perspective. This reflection must be openly presented, formulated and communicated in a way that is easy to find and generally understandable.

Additional explanation: The chosen methods can be technologies, software, tools, forms of integration, data collection methods, etc.

18. The chosen methods and content of the project must be designed to be as inclusive as possible. If the methods and content cannot be designed to be inclusive, or can only be partially inclusive, the reasons for this must be described.

Additional explanation: For understandable reasons, not every project can involve everyone. This is not necessary to meet this criterion. If certain methods cannot be designed to be inclusive, the reasons for this must be described. Inclusive methods and content appeal to all people and all people feel included. Inclusive methods and content are understandable to everyone. All people can participate and make decisions.

19. Generally understandable information on the handling of research data in the project must be published and made available prior to any collaboration. This includes information on the publication of research data according to criterion 9.

Additional explanation: Research data does not generally refer to personal data, the handling of which is already regulated by legislation (e.g. General Data Protection Regulation).

20. Citizen scientists must be acknowledged in an appropriate and meaningful way when presenting the results of the project.

Additional explanation: A meaningful way of acknowledgement cannot be described in general terms, as it is always project-specific.

21. A data management plan must be developed before data collection begins.